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(ABSTRACTS)

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TITLE: Store Image - A Critical Success Factor in Dynamic Retailing Environment: An Investigation

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ABSTRACT

The main motto of this paper was to analyze the relationship between store image and customer behavior and furthermore, to examine the influence of store image on customer behavior. Customers of mall based specialty stores (n=200) were surveyed on random basis through printed questionnaires by face to face interview during January-February 2011. The validity of scales used in questionnaire was measured through face & content validity method. The reliability of the scale was assessed through the adaption of the research of Copper and Schindler. The internal consistency of reliability was measured by calculating Cronbach's Alfa. One sample t-test and Kolmogorov-Smirnov one sample test have been used to data analysis and hypothesis testing. The results of the study showed a positive relationship between store image and variables of customer behavior viz... purchase making decisions, purchase intention, make a purchase, impulse purchase, frequency to visit, time spend in store, maintain customer interest, store choice, store satisfaction, store revisit, positive word of mouth, life style, attitude, benefits, leanings, perception, and motivation. Furthermore, results also depict a high degree of positive influence of store image on customer behavior. The study was confined to only Pune City of Maharashtra state. The study will be helpful to the responsible management of mall based specialty stores to create more impressive and inviting store image. The study will further prove to be a great help to the researchers who want to do similar or related research.